

SOLUTIONS OF NEWTON INTERPOLATION PROBLEMS USING THE PYTHON PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

Gulshan S. Ergashkhojaye

Master Of Namangan State University

E-mail: gulshanergashxojoyeva0621@gmail.com

Abstract: This article investigates the theoretical and practical aspects of constructing the Newton interpolation polynomial, a key method for function approximation. Furthermore, it demonstrates the steps for determining coefficients by constructing a system of linear equations based on given datasets. In the practical section, Python programming code and algorithms for calculating the Newton polynomial using the Gauss elimination method are provided

Keywords: Newton interpolation, interpolation nodes, polynomial, system of linear equations, Gauss elimination, Python, algorithm design.

NYUTON INTERPOLYATSIYA MASALALARINI PYTHON DASTURLASH TILIDA YECHISH

Namangan davlat universiteti magistranti

Ergashxo'jayeva Gulshan Sadirdin qizi

E-mail: gulshanergashxojoyeva0621@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada funksiyalarni yaqinlashtirishning muhim usullaridan biri bo'lgan Nyuton interpolatsiya ko'phadini qurish masalasi nazariy va amaliy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Maqolaning amaliy qismida Gauss usuli yordamida Nyuton ko'phadini hisoblovchi Python dasturiy kodi va algoritmlari taqdim etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nyuton interpolatsiyasi, interpolatsiya tugunlari, ko'phad, chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi, Gauss usuli, Python, algoritmlash.

Amaliy hisoblashlarda Nyutonning interpolyatsiyalashga oid ikki xil formulasi keng qo'llaniladi. Nyutonning birinchi interpolyatsiya formulasi yordamida $y = f(x)$

funksiyaning qiymatini x_0 boshlang'ich nuqtaga yaqin joylarda aniqlash qulay hisoblanadi. Shu sababli bu formula jadvalning bosh qismidagi qiymatlar bilan ishlashda samarali bo'ladi, biroq jadval oxiridagi nuqtalar uchun hisoblash biroz noqulaylik tug'diradi. Nyutonning ikkinchi interpolyatsiya formulasi esa, aksincha, kesmaning oxirgi nuqtasi x_n dan boshlab orqaga qarab hisoblashga asoslanadi.

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n tugun nuqtalardagi

$$y_0 = f(x_0), \quad y_1 = f(x_1), \quad \dots, \quad y_n = f(x_n)$$

Qiymatlar bilan berilgan bo'lsin,

$$N_n(x_0) = y_0, \quad N_n(x_1) = y_1, \quad \dots, \quad N_n(x_n) = y_n$$

Tengliklarni qanoatlantiruvchi $N_n(x)$ ko'phadni qurish talab qilinmoqda. n -darajali i ko'phadning mavjudlik va yagonalik shartidan kelib chiqib, uni quyidagi tenglama ko'rinishida ifodalanadi.

$$N_n(x_i) = d_0 + d_1(x_i - x_0) + d_2(x_i - x_0)(x_i - x_1) + \dots \\ + d_n(x_i - x_0)(x_i - x_1) \dots (x_i - x_{n-1}) = f(x_i), \quad i = 0..n$$

Nyuton interpolyatsiya ko'phadi

$N_n(x)$ ning noma'lum $d_i, i=0,1,\dots,n$ koeffitsientlarini interpolyatsiya shartlaridan topamiz:

$$N_n(x_i) = d_0 + d_1(x_i - x_0) + d_2(x_i - x_0)(x_i - x_1) + \dots \\ + d_n(x_i - x_0)(x_i - x_1) \dots (x_i - x_{n-1}) = f(x_i), \quad i = 0..n$$

Biz quyi chap uchburchak matritsali tenglamalar sistemasini olamiz:

$$d_0 = f(x_0), \\ d_0 + d_1(x_1 - x_0) = f(x_1), \\ d_0 + d_1(x_2 - x_0) + d_2(x_2 - x_0)(x_2 - x_1) = f(x_2), \\ \dots \\ d_0 + d_1(x_n - x_0)(x_n - x_1) + \dots + d_n(x_n - x_0) \dots (x_n - x_{n-1}) = f(x_n).$$

Bu quyidagi uchburchak matritsali chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi eng birinchi tenglamadan boshlab yechiladi:

$$d_0 = f(x_0), \quad d_1 = \frac{[f(x_1) - f(x_0)]}{x_1 - x_0} = f[x_0, x_1],$$

$$f(x_0) + f[x_0, x_1](x_2 - x_0) + d_2(x_2 - x_0)(x_2 - x_1) = f(x_2) \Rightarrow f[x_0, x_1, x_2].$$

Va matematik induksiya bo'yicha, $d_k = f[x_0, x_1, \dots, x_k], k \leq n$.

Demak, interpolatsiya ko'phadining Nyuton ko'rinish quyidagicha bo'ladi.

$$N_n(f; x) = f(x_0) + f[x_0, x_1](x - x_0) + \dots + f[x_0, \dots, x_n](x - x_0) \dots (x - x_{n-1})$$

Yuqoridagi tenglama Nyutonning 1-interpolatsiya formulasi deyiladi.

Agar $x_1 - x_0 = \dots = x_n - x_{n-1}$ bo'lsa $\frac{x-x_0}{h} = t$ deb ushbu formulani hosil qilamiz:

$$N_n(f; x) = f(x_0) + hf[x_0, x_1]t + \dots + h^n f[x_0, \dots, x_n]t(t-1) \dots (t-n+1), x = x_0 + th$$

Nyutonning 1-interpolatsiya formulasida interpolatsiya x_0 nuqtadan boshlanadi. Nyutonning 2-interpolatsiya formulasida esa interpolatsiya x_n nuqtadan boshlanadi:

$$N_n(f; x) = f(x_n) + f[x_{n-1}, x_n](x - x_n) + \dots + f[x_0, \dots, x_n](x - x_n) \dots (x - x_1)$$

Tenglamani keltirib chiqarishda paydo bo'ladigan chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi, yuqori o'ng burchak sistemadan iborat bo'ladi va noma'lumlar $d_n, d_{n-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0$ tartibda topib boriladi. Demak Nyutonga chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi va ularning yechilishi mumkin bo'lgan sodda hollari ma'lum bo'lgan.

Masalaning qo'yilishi:

X	2	1	0	-1
Y	4	5	6	2

Nyuton interpolatsion ko'phadini tuzing.

Masalaning Python dasturlash muhitidagi yechimi

Dastur kodi;

```
Import numpy as np
def gauss_elimination(A,b):
n=len(b)
A=A.astype(float)
b=b.astype(float)
for I in range(n):
    #diagonal elementni 1 ga aylantiramiz
    pivot=A[i,i]
    A[i]=A[i]/pivot
    b[i]=b[i]/pivot
    for j in range(i+1, n):
        factor=A[j,i]
        A[j]=A[j]-factor*A[i]
        b[j]=b[j]-factor*b[i]
    #orqaga qaytish usuli (Back Substitution)
    x=np.zeros(n)
    for I in range(n-1,-1,-1):
        x[i]=b[i]-np.dot(A[i, i+1:], x[i+1:])
    return x
x_vals=np.array([2, 1, 0, -1])
y_vals=np.array([4, 5, 6, 2])
A=np.array([[1, 2, 4, 8] [1, 1, 1, 1] [1, 0, 0, 0] [1, -1, 1, -1]])
b=y_vals
coeffs=gauss_elimination(A, b)
print("Nyuton interpolatsiya ko'phadining koeffitsientlari:")
```

```
print(f'a0={coeffs[0]}')  
print(f'a1={coeffs[1]}')  
print(f'a2={coeffs[2]}')  
print(f'a3={coeffs[3]}')  
print("\nInterpolyatsiya qilingan ko'phad:")  
print(f'P(x)= {coeffs[0]} +{coeffs[1]}*x+{coeffs[2]}*x^2+{coeffs[3]}*x^3')
```

Natija:

Nyuton interpolyatsiya ko'phadining koeffisientlari:

$a_0=6.0000000000000001$

$a_1=0.66666666666666661$

$a_2=-2.5$

$a_3=0.8333333333333334$

Interpolyatsiya qilingan ko'phad:

$P(x)=6.0000000000000001+0.66666666666666661*x+-$
 $2.5*x^2+0.8333333333333334*x^3[1].$

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